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“HOW I WISH TO BE LOVED BY THE SOLDIER”

Every time I see a soldier, my heart races with delight,
His grace and poise make my soul love, yet never belong.
Yes, I fell for the soldier—and it always shattered me inside,
A love that's doomed to fade, a truth I couldn't hide.

He has a family, and I am gay—
Though we're close, I know he'll never stay.
When he's on leave for Rest and Recreation,
I ache with silent desperation—
For though I long to be with him,
His time is spent with them.

What role do I play in his life, I ask?
A helper in shadows, a quiet task.
A supporter, a provider—that's all I seem to be,
A truth that weighs so heavily on me.
My love for this soldier is both passion and pain,
A heartache that echoes again and again.

I am gay, and he is not—
So love, I know, is something I have not.
All he can offer is friendship's hand,
But not the love I'd hoped would stand.

This painful truth is mine to bear,
My heart cries out in silent prayer.
Still, I must face what I've started—
The consequences cannot be undone.
And though it hurts, I choose to stay,
Because I love him—come what may.
Someday, I know he'll go home,
And I'll be left here in the quiet, alone.

But my heart, my soul, my being—
Will stay here, loving him.
Forever.

